

SPIRITUAL INTELLIGENCE IN RELATION TO ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AMONG B.ED STUDENTS

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Cite This Article: P. Sujatha & Dr. R. Annadurai, "Spiritual Intelligence in Relation to Academic Achievement among B.Ed Students", International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 422-425, 2018.

Abstract:

Spirituality is derived from the Latin word "Spirare" meaning to breathe. Spirituality is inherent aspect of human nature and essence of our existence so it draws attention of many theorists as the source of all thoughts, feelings, values and behaviour. Variations of spiritual intelligence are sometimes used in corporate settings, as a means of motivating employees. Providing a non-religious, diversity-sensitive framework for addressing issues of values in the workplace. According to Stephen Covey, "Spiritual intelligence is the central and most fundamental of all the intelligences, because it becomes the source of guidance for the others" Spiritual Intelligence (SQ). According to Webster's dictionary the word "Spirit" defines as "the animating or vital principle: that which gives life to the physical organism in contrast to its material elements: the breath of life".

Key Words: Spiritual Intelligence and Academic Achievement

Need for the Study:

Spiritual intelligence has become an important part of our lives as well as workplace. Spirituality is considered as one of the key factors for the success of the educational organizations and ultimately for the professional life of the teacher. The spiritual perspective is causing shift in the workplace values promoting cooperation rather than fear at the work place. Spirituality in the workplace as a framework proves the role of organizational values in a culture and the role of spirituality is important in creating and instilling values and culture in an organization. When people have high spirituality in the workplace, it may be more responsible for the organization and they have a high loyalty. Spiritual intelligence, using a multisensory approach to access one's inner knowledge to solve global problems, could be an integrating theme to create global awareness among teachers and students. Having realized the potential of spiritual intelligence, different Educational Commissions have recommended that spiritual aspects are needed for the harmonious development of the learner. International commission on Education for Twenty-first century (UNESCO, 1996) says that "Education should contribute to every person's complete development-mind and body, intelligence, sensitivity, aesthetics, appreciation and spirituality". Spiritual intelligence which will be the highest guidance to them to carry out their functions as educators with the highest regards and as noble as possible. This is because teachers are regarded someone very high in society. So, the investigator is concerned the study on the B.Ed. students spiritual intelligence level is relates to their academic achievement level. The investigator took up the study and entitled it, "Spiritual Intelligence in Relation to Academic Achievement among B.Ed Students in Madurai District".

Terms and Definitions:

Spiritual Intelligence: Refers to the holistic concept in incorporating mind, body and spirit. It is the intelligence with which persons address and solve problems with meaning and other values of life.

Academic Achievement: Refers to the marks secured in I year-end examinations, conducted by Tamil Nadu Teacher's Education University.

B.Ed Students: Refers to those who are studying 2nd year undergraduate education degree in Madurai District.

Variables of the Study:

The study has been designed the following variables.

Dependent Variables:

- Spiritual intelligence
- Academic Achievement

Independent Variables:

- Gender : Male / Female
- Religion : Hindu / Others

Objectives of the Study:

To specify objectives of the present study are listed below:

- To measure the level of spiritual intelligence among B.Ed students in Madurai District.
- To find out whether there is significant difference in spiritual intelligence among B.Ed. students in terms of select independent variables viz. Gender, Religion,.
- To measure the level of academic achievement among B.Ed. students in Madurai District.

- To find out whether there is significant difference in academic achievement among B.Ed. students in terms of select independent variables viz. Gender, Religion,.
- To find out the relationship between the spiritual intelligence and academic achievement among B.Ed students in Madurai District.

Hypotheses of the Study:

- Gender exerts a significant influence on spiritual intelligence among B.Ed. students.
- Religion exerts a significant influence on spiritual intelligence among B.Ed. students.
- Gender exerts a significant influence on academic achievement among B.Ed. students.
- Religion exerts a significant influence on academic achievement among B.Ed. students.
- There is a positive relationship between spiritual intelligence and academic achievement among B.Ed. students in Madurai District.

Methodology in Brief:

Sample: A stratified representative sample of 364 B.Ed Students from seven colleges of education from Madurai district with due representation given to select independent variables.

Tools Used:

- “Spiritual Intelligence Inventory” Constructed and Standardized by Leka. V (2017).
- General Information Sheet.

Statistical Treatment:

- t test for significance of difference between the means of large independent samples.
- Test of product moment correlation r.

Related Studies:

Asthana (2011) conducted a study on a sample of 300 students consisting 150 male and 150 female students of secondary education from Varanasi, with a view to assess to gender difference in scholastic achievement. Scholastic achievement was measured on the basis of an average of marks obtained in three previous annual examinations. The findings revealed that there was a significant difference in academic achievement of male and female students. Girls were found to be better performers than boys.

Sharma and Tahira (2011) investigated the influence of parental education, parental occupation and family size on science achievement of the secondary school students in western Uttar Pradesh in India. 1500 students were selected as a sample for the study and data was collected through a questionnaire that assessed personal information and science achievement test developed by the researchers themselves. The results indicated that family variables including parental education had significant relationship with the achievement of their children. Hence, it could be concluded that the gender and geographical area in which the student live and are exposed may influence academic success of the students at all levels of education. Gender, locale and Parental education have direct influence on the academic achievement of the students.

Hypothesis 1: Gender exerts a significant influence on spiritual intelligence among B.Ed. students.

The results of tests of significance of difference between the mean scores of Spiritual intelligence among B.Ed. students in terms of sex are presented in Table 1.

Variable	Sub- variables	No. of Students	Mean	Standard deviation	“t” Value	Significance at 0.05 level
Gender	Male	58	36.55	4.12	-0.112	Not Significance
	Female	306	36.62	4.46		

The calculated „t” value (-0.112) is lower than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level. This shows that there is no significant difference between Male and Female in possession of spiritual intelligence among B.Ed. students. It can be inferred from the above finding that, sex does not influence on Spiritual Intelligence among B.Ed. Students. Hence the Hypothesis 1 is rejected.

Hypothesis 2: Religion exerts a significant influence on spiritual intelligence among B.Ed. students.

The results of tests of significance of difference between the mean scores of Spiritual intelligence among B.Ed. Students in terms of religion are presented in Table 2 .

Variable	Sub- variables	No. of students	Mean	Standard deviation	“t” Value	Significance at 0.05 level
Religion	Hindu	292	36.40	4.614	-2.198	Significance
	Others	72	37.44	3.314		

The calculated „t” value (-2.198) is greater than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level. This shows that there is a significant difference between Hindu and Other students in possession of spiritual intelligence among B.Ed. students. It can be inferred from the above finding that, other religions B.Ed. students possess more of spiritual intelligence than Hindu B.Ed. students. Hence the hypothesis 2 is accepted.

Hypothesis 3: Gender exerts a significant influence on academic achievement among B.Ed. students.

The results of tests of significance of difference between the mean scores of Academic Achievement among B.Ed. students in terms of sex presented in Table 3.

Variable	Sub-variables	No. of students	Mean	Standard deviation	“t” Value	Significance at 0.05 level
Gender	Male	58	76.98	9.118	0.107	Not Significance
	Female	306	76.84	10.128		

The calculated “t” value (0.107) is lower than the table value (1.96) at 0/05 level. This shows that there is no significant difference between Male and Female in possession of Academic Achievement among B.Ed. students. It can be inferred from the above finding that, sex does not influence on Academic Achievement among B.Ed. Students. Hence the hypothesis 9 is rejected.

Hypothesis 4: Religion exerts a significant influence on academic achievement among B.Ed. students.

The results of tests of significance of difference between the mean scores of Academic Achievement among B.Ed. students in terms of religion are presented in Table 4.

Variable	Sub- variables	No. of students	Mean	Standard deviation	“t” Value	Significance at 0.05 level
Religion	Hindu	292	76.76	9.950	0.405	Not Significance
	Others	72	77.29	10.071		

The calculated “t”- value (0.405) is lower than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level. This shows that there is no significant difference between Hindu and Other students in possession of Academic Achievement among B.Ed. students. It can be inferred from the above finding that, religion not play a vital role in the possession of Academic Achievement among B.Ed. students. Hence the hypothesis 10 is rejected.

Conclusions:

The major conclusions emerged out of the present study are presented below:

- Spiritual Intelligence among B.Ed., students are found to be well above the average.
- Spiritual intelligence level is found independent on Gender.
- Academic Achievement among B.Ed. students is found to be well above the average.
- Academic Achievement level is found independent upon Gender, and Religio.
- There is a significantly positive relationship between spiritual intelligence and academic achievement among B.Ed. students.

Educational Implications:

A research tool-Spiritual Intelligence Inventory among B.Ed. students was prepared and standardized by the investigator with the consultation of the guide. This is highly useful for the students” teachers, policy makers, administrators and practitioners in the field of teacher education. Religion plays a vital role in spiritual intelligence among B.Ed. students. The out of the research shows that other religion B.Ed. students do well in spiritual intelligence than Hindu religion B.Ed. students. Efforts should be taken for the upliftment of the spiritual intelligence among the Hindu religion students for their betterment of B.Ed. students” spiritual intelligence immediately.

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